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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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**6-International Humanitarian Law
Implications During the War in Ukraine:
Problems and Violations. By Oleksandr
Khomenko and others. p. 123.**

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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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**A GROUP OF UNIVERSITY GRADUATES IN UKRAINE
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**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
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INTERNATIONAL HUMANITARIAN LAW IMPLICATIONS DURING THE WAR IN UKRAINE: PROBLEMS AND VIOLATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Basic social values must be protected both in peacetime and during armed conflict. Current geopolitical developments, particularly the Russian-Ukrainian war, highlight rising threats to international security and systematic violations of humanitarian law. This study explores challenges to the legitimacy and enforcement of international humanitarian law (IHL), focusing on key rights such as life, peace, health, and security. It assesses the role of international legal institutions in ensuring these protections and examines how legal regulation shapes social safeguards during war. Special attention is given to the concept of hybrid warfare as a hallmark of

modern conflict. The research identifies the limited impact of existing sanctions on IHL violators and analyzes human rights protection at both national and international levels. It also stresses that terrorism remains prohibited under IHL, even in wartime. The study concludes with a call for stronger legal mechanisms, effective sanctions, and guaranteed humanitarian access to uphold humanitarian standards.

Keywords: human rights, domestic law, implementation, fraud during the war, humanitarian aid, international humanitarian law, money transfers, charitable foundations, war crimes, criminal liability, crime.

1- INTRODUCTION

Trends in the development of international law and democratization of social relations is accompanied by an increased risk of violation of humanitarian norms due to active military threats. It becomes obvious that the leveling of these risks cannot currently be implemented through the mediation of relevant interstate political agreements or interaction of civil defense forces with the armed forces.

Against the backdrop of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict, fundamental humanitarian rights have not found proper guarantees in the international legal field. The functionality of global institutions in the context of sanctions policy currently requires revision and updating. Modern experts on the theoretical and practical aspects of legal regulation of civil security and humanitarian foundations during the war in Ukraine analyze the system of identifying threats and effectively responding to them, regulating manifestations of socio-political instability, and are unanimous in their conclusions regarding the need to rethink the value context of international humanitarian law as a guarantee of fundamental humanitarian guarantees in any, even the most crisis-like conditions.¹ Given the acute relevance of the topic, the research issues go beyond the Russian-Ukrainian conflict and are of scientific and practical value for the global upgrade of the international legal field.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

¹ Ivankiv, I. B. (2020). *The rights of humanity*. Vaite; Onishchenko, N. M. (2020). *Law and progress: Demands of civil society*. Naukova dumka; Onishchenko, N. M., & Suniehin, S. O. (2023). Legal support of interaction between the Armed Forces of Ukraine and civil society: Conceptual framework. *Scientific Innovations and Advanced Technologies*, 5(19), 313–321; Nonyak, M. (2024). Security as a prerequisite for the realization of the human right to peace. *Scientific Perspectives*, 1(43), 691–699; Kresin, O. (2022). The nature of the powers and acts of the UN General Assembly: Statutory provisions and the evolution of their interpretation. *Law of Ukraine*, 7, 112–120.

The problem of updating the principles of international humanitarian law has now reached a fundamentally new stage of development. Sytnyk² and Parkhomenko,³ investigating aspects of legal regulation of the protection of the civilian population during the war in Ukraine, note that the phenomenon of military aggression was considered an international crime by the Rome Statute.

Modern authors note the ineffectiveness of the Hague and Geneva Conventions, which for decades have been positioned as the fundamental levers for regulating modern international humanitarian law.⁴ In particular, this has been clearly demonstrated by the events in Ukraine.

Scholars also highlight the negative impact of corruption in Ukraine on ensuring fundamental human rights and freedoms during wartime.⁵ At the same time, Ishchenko et al.,⁶ Kortukova et al.,⁷ Lepskiy and Lepska,⁸ Usmanov and Vergeles,⁹ analyzing human rights in martial law, explore the potential of international legal and institutional support as the basis of humanitarian law in a global dimension. Scientists actualize the issues of the lack of stable guarantees of compliance with established and generally recognized international standards, as well as the shortage of effective tools for the development of the democratic process.

² Sytnyk, H. P. (2023). *Filosofia viiny ta myru: Kurs leksii* [Philosophy of war and peace: Lecture course]. TOV «SAK Ltd.».

³ Parkhomenko, N. M. (2023). *Law-making and law-creation under martial law and peacebuilding*. Parliamentary Publishing House.

⁴ Izarova, I., Prytyka, Y., Uhrynovska, O., & Shestopalov, N. (2023). Protection of rights of internally displaced persons amid military aggression in Ukraine. *The Age of Human Rights Journal*, 20. <https://doi.org/10.17561/tahrj.v20.7802>; Moisiyakha, A. (2022). Formation of state policy of humanitarian support during the period of military conflict. *Public Governance*, 3(31), 38–45.

⁵ Dill, J., & Schubiger, L. (2021). Attitudes toward the use of force: Instrumental imperatives, moral principles, and international law. *American Journal of Political Science*, 65(3), 612–633. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajps.12636>

⁶ Ishchenko, Y., Chystovska, Y., Vovchenko, O., Harkusha, I., & Voshkolup, H. (2023). The role of emotional intelligence in the rehabilitation of former prisoners of war. *International Journal of Statistics in Medical Research*, 12, 240–248. <https://doi.org/10.9734/IJSMR/2023/v12i230289>

⁷ Kortukova, T., Kolosovskiy, Y., Korolchuk, O. L., Shchokin, R., & Volkov, A. S. (2023). Peculiarities of the legal regulation of temporary protection in the European Union in the context of the aggressive war of the Russian Federation against Ukraine. *International Journal for the Semiotics of Law*, 36(2), 667–678. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11196-023-09943-6>

⁸ Lepskiy, M., & Lepska, N. (2023). The war in Ukraine and its challenge to NATO: Peacekeeping to peace engineering. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 67(3), 402–425. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00027642231155895>

⁹ Usmanov, Yu. I., & Vergeles, O. (2022). The problem of humanitarian access in conditions of armed conflicts. *Scientific Bulletin of Uzhhorod National University. Series: Law*, 69, 461–466.

Facts of violations of humanitarian law are investigated in academic circles with regard to the wars in Yugoslavia and Syria. For example, Sriram et al.¹⁰ implemented a comprehensive analysis of the facts of violations and strategies for their elimination in the military conflicts in Sudan, Yugoslavia, Congo and Sierra Leone. Scientists assess in detail the effectiveness of institutional and legal guarantees of compliance with the norms of international humanitarian law, analyze the imbalance between the established system of protection fundamental humanitarian requirements regarding methods of warfare.

Aspects of the practical effectiveness of humanitarian law in modern armed conflicts are also explored by Wallace,¹¹ Karreth et al.,¹² Rhoads and Sutton,¹³ Sunga.¹⁴ The authors are characterized by diametrically different positions on the assessment of the institutional capacity of the international legislative and legal field in the context of guarantees of the basic requirements of humanitarian law in times of war. It is worth noting that more recent publications note the low level of effectiveness of the existing humanitarian regulation mechanisms in armed conflicts, which indicates the rapid evolution of the definition of basic humanitarian rights and the need to upgrade approaches to the guarantees of the latter.

The purpose of the study is to analyze specific challenges to the legitimacy of international humanitarian law during the war in Ukraine.

3. METHOD

The study is a descriptive scientific research. The main materials used were professional industry publications indexed in major scientometric databases (in particular, Scopus, Web of Science), scientific papers, legislative acts and statistical information. To optimize the search, the keywords “human rights, humanitarian law, civil protection, international law, martial law, social rights, national security” were used. Preference was given to publications from the 2020-2025 sample.

In the process of working on the article, a number of general scientific methods were used, including the structural-logical method, analysis, synthesis, generalization,

¹⁰ Sriram, C. L., Martin-Ortega, O., & Herman, J. (2017). *War, conflict and human rights: Theory and practice*. Routledge.

¹¹ Wallace, G. P. (2019). Condemning or condoning the perpetrators? International humanitarian law and attitudes toward wartime violence. *Law & Social Inquiry*, 44(1), 192–226. <https://doi.org/10.1017/lsi.2018.25>

¹² Karreth, J., Sullivan, P. L., & Dezfuli, G. (2020). Explaining how human rights protections change after internal armed conflicts. *Journal of Global Security Studies*, 5(2), 248–264. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jogss/ogz059>

¹³ Rhoads, E. P., & Sutton, R. (2020). The (self) protection of civilians in South Sudan: Popular and community justice practices. *African Affairs*, 119(476), 370–394. <https://doi.org/10.1093/afraf/adz027>

¹⁴ Sunga, L. S. (2021). *Individual responsibility in international law for serious human rights violations* (Vol. 21). BRILL. <https://books.google.com.ua/books?hl=uk&lr=&id=f7FFEAAAQBAJme>

and systematization. These methods were adapted to the context of this study in the context of military conflicts.

The historical method was used to study the specifics of the evolution of the phenomenon of international humanitarian law, as well as the comparative law method to identify key determinants of the impact on the processes of ensuring the fundamental rights and freedoms of the civilian population during armed conflicts.

To form conclusions, the method of abstraction was used, the essence of which consisted in a mental detachment from standard concepts with the simultaneous selection of essential properties adapted to the context of the study. With the help of scientific abstraction, the essence of international humanitarian law during the war in Ukraine was determined.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The system of international humanitarian law is composed of a number of normative and legal acts implemented in the global legal field. Given the focus of this study on the challenges and violations of human rights and freedoms during the war in Ukraine, it is necessary to emphasize the documents that are decisive in international humanitarian law in the context of this particular country. In particular, the basic legislative norms include the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ratified in Ukraine in 1997),¹⁵ International Covenants on Various Kinds of Rights,¹⁶ Universal Declaration of Human Rights,¹⁷ Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime¹⁸ and a number of others. The core important principles of IHL are summarized in Figure 1 below.

International humanitarian law determine prohibitions and restrictions on the use of violence during armed conflicts. International humanitarian law, first of all, puts forward requirements to spare civilians and those who have ceased to take a direct part in hostilities, as well as to limit violence as much as possible.

In conditions of military operations, it is necessary to ensure guarantees of compliance with basic humanitarian requirements enshrined in the international legal framework.¹⁹ These categories underlie the concept of civilian security and are a prerequisite for a productive life. The norms of international humanitarian law determine a list of entities that must be provided with protection guarantees. These include:

- the civilian population under occupation;

¹⁵ **Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms. (1997). Council of Europe.**

¹⁶ **International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. (1973). United Nations.**

¹⁷ **Universal Declaration of Human Rights. (1948). United Nations General Assembly.**

¹⁸ **Convention on Cybercrime. (2006). Council of Europe.**

¹⁹ **Dill and Schubiger (2021), "Attitudes toward the use of force," 612–33.**

- prisoners of war;
- sick, wounded combatants, or those who have suffered a shipwreck;
- combatants - participants of the armed conflict, regarding guarantees of protection from means and methods of warfare that lead to excessive suffering or inevitable death.²⁰

Important principles of IHL

Principle of distinction: Always distinguish between fighters and military aims and civilians and civilian items.

Principle of proportionality: Requires parties to anticipate incidental harm that might be caused directly by an attack and the indirect effects, provided that they are reasonably foreseeable.

Principle of precaution: Requires all parties to an armed conflict to conduct all military actions with continual caution to avoid harming people or civilian-related items.

Figure 1. The core principles of IHL

Source: Crowe and Weston-Scheuber²¹

In general, the basis for the development of international humanitarian law is a set of key values of the human-centric concept. At the same time, there is an interdisciplinary institute of restriction of rights, which is valid, including during the period of establishment of special legal regimes (martial law).²²

The reason for partial or complete restriction of human rights is a direct threat to national interests. As represented by the practice of international activity, the European Convention determines the basic criteria for restriction of rights that meet the requirements of legality:

- The fact of enshrining such restrictions in the legislative field;
- The legality of the purpose of the said restrictions;

²⁰ Izarova et al., *Protection of rights of internally displaced persons, 2023*; Moisiyakha, *Formation of state policy of humanitarian support, 2022*.

²¹ Crowe, J., & Weston-Scheuber, K. (2013). *Principles of international humanitarian law*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

²² Ishchenko et al., "The role of emotional intelligence," 240–48; Kortukova et al., "Peculiarities of the legal regulation," 667–78.

- The inevitable need for restrictions, their lack of alternatives.

The types of lawful restrictions on human rights and freedoms defined by international humanitarian law include:

- Restrictions during an emergency situation (enshrined in Article 15 of the European Convention);

- The need to regulate the political activities of foreigners (determined by Article 16 of the European Convention);

- Restrictions to prevent abuse of rights (defined in Article 17 of the European Convention).

The potential for rights of humanitarian protection restrictions during war and armed conflicts requires the establishment of a stable system of guarantee.²³ In particular, the duration of the introduction of restrictions on rights cannot be longer than the duration of martial law; the possibility of torture, the use of cruel punishment or degrading treatment, as well as the introduction of restrictions on the right to freedom of thought, religion, and conscience must be completely excluded.²⁴

Any violation of these requirements may be appealed within the limits set by the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (Article 33). The provisions of this Convention serve as the basis for establishing a violation of human rights. The European Court of Human Rights is also guided by the norms of the Geneva Conventions for the Protection of War Victims (1949), the European Social Charter (1961), and the European Convention for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (1987).

In the context of the war in Ukraine, the obvious inconsistency of the norms of the realities of the armed conflict with the requirements of international humanitarian law is characteristic. The concept of hybrid war, which is absent from the norms of the international legal field, is emerging and actively integrated. Hybrid war, in essence, is an innovative type of external aggression using various actions and means prohibited by international law to achieve strategic goals.²⁵ The basis of hybrid warfare is positioned as informational and psychological influence on public consciousness, which is difficult to identify. The specificity of the Russian Federation's hybrid war against Ukraine lies in the disregard for international requirements regarding the humanitarian law, the use of network warfare tactics, cyberterrorism, the involvement of mercenaries not identified by international legal norms, etc.

The outlined problem of hybrid warfare, among other things, actualizes the improvement of the norms of international law in this context. The fundamental postulates of international humanitarian law, enshrined in the Geneva and Hague

²³ Sytnyk, *Filosofia viiny ta myru*, 2023; Parkhomenko, *Law-making and law-creation*, 2023.

²⁴ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 1973.

²⁵ Hudson, J. (2023). *Wartime governance in the Syrian civil war*. Palgrave Macmillan.

Conventions, highlight the priority of protecting civilians during war or occupation. The Russian Federation deliberately neglects these requirements, destroying civilian infrastructure, carrying out mass executions, rape and torture of civilians, causing a humanitarian catastrophe. The actions of the Russian Federation in occupied cities are a direct violation of the Geneva Convention relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War.

A blatant violation of generally accepted norms of humanitarian law by the aggressor – Russia is the treatment of prisoners of war. Among other things, numerous violations of the requirements of the Geneva Convention relative to the Treatment of Prisoners of War (1949) have been recorded. The Russians are ignoring direct prohibition of torture, ill-treatment and abuse of prisoners of war, abuse, which is documented in a voluminous evidence base. The use of prohibited types of weapons is also a violation on the part of the Russian Federation. It is obvious that the actions of the Russian Federation are due to the lack of an effective deterrent.

Separately, it is necessary to emphasize the problem of humanitarian access, which provides for the unhindered access by authorized humanitarian organizations, which guarantees support for people in need to support their lives and is regulated by the Geneva Convention (Articles 17, 23), the First Additional Protocol to the Geneva Conventions (Articles 54, 70, 71) and other norms of international humanitarian law. Today, there is a critical complication of humanitarian access as a concept of the aggressor's military strategy: constant shelling, contamination of the territory with weapons, illegal expropriation of provisions, increased risks for humanitarian missions are causing a large-scale humanitarian catastrophe in Ukraine.

The risks of terrorism as a critical violation of humanitarian law in times of war require special attention. The current international legal framework establishes the prohibition of terrorism in the context of a means of warfare in two provisions: Article 51 of Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions (1949) and Article 33 of the Fourth Geneva Convention. Given the events in Ukraine, the Russian Federation appears as a terrorist country, for which the usual methods of waging war are intimidation and threats, terrorist acts. A striking example is brutal extermination of prisoners of war in the Ukrainian Olenivka, which is regarded as the maximum violation of the humanitarian law.

Thus, in the crisis conditions of the war in Ukraine, fundamental international documents are often endowed with declarative nature, and the global system of control over compliance with their requirements is not sufficiently functional. This determines the need to upgrade the mechanisms for protecting fundamental human rights and freedoms through the transformation of international judicial and human rights organizations. Among the priority areas is the development of a global Code of International Sanctions with a provision for a system of serious penalties for deliberate violation of generally established requirements of international legislation in the field of humanitarian law. After all, the main problem at present is not the potential consolidation of humanitarian norms and requirements in the international legal field, but a practical system of guarantees for their implementation.

The issue of guarantees of compliance with humanitarian rights enshrined in the international legal field forms debatable aspects of scientific discourse. Fysekis²⁶ analyzes aspects of the destructive impact of war on the humanitarian situation and determines the ineffectiveness of existing mechanisms of guarantees protection of the humanitarian foundations of social development. The author's position is complementary the conclusions of this study regarding the need to improve existing international systems of legal guarantees relating to the protection of civilians.

Lobna²⁷ emphasizes the need to develop an effective system for identifying civilians and military personnel, as well as the formation of effective international institutions to guarantee compliance with the humanitarian legal framework, the decisions of which will be binding. It is seen that the position of the scientist is not new, but very relevant today. Humanitarian law requires unquestioning compliance with the basic concepts by all parties to the conflict, and the proposal of Lobna²⁸ is extremely relevant.

Johnson,²⁹ Mutuma and Mutunga,³⁰ exploring the aspects of differentiation of permissible and prohibited actions in times of war, emphasise the need for guarantees of compliance with the norms of humanitarian law enshrined in the international legal field, because the human rights to life and to peace are the basis of the human-centric principles of democratic development. The commonality in the authors' results is seen in the need to intensify the participation of the international democratic community in the strategies of protection of humanitarian law and the peaceful settlement of military conflicts, and the actualization of the dependence of the humanitarian concept of social development on the powers of influential geopolitical players.

The position of researchers Rawtani et al.,³¹ Pereira et al.,³² and Bowden and Metcalfe-Hough³³ is interesting, who determine a safe environment as a basic

²⁶ Fysekis, A. (2020). Protection of population in times of war. *Diplomacy & Intelligence / Revistă de Științe Sociale, Diplomatie și Studii de Securitate*, 14, 196–207.

²⁷ Lobna, M. (2022). The identity and protection of civilians in international humanitarian law. *Des noms, des êtres et des récits d'identités*, 10(1).

²⁸ Lobna, "The identity and protection of civilians," 2022.

²⁹ Johnson, J. (2021). Armed conflict and the protection of populations: The debate over humanitarian intervention, using armed force, and the idea of sovereignty. *The Brown Journal of World Affairs*, 28, 185–203.

³⁰ Mutuma, K., & Mutunga, N. (2022). Civilian protection in war; an insurmountable task? Prohibited & legally permissible conduct during hostilities. *Journal of Conflict Management & Sustainable Development*, 8(4).

³¹ Rawtani, D., Gupta, G., Khatri, N., & Rao, P. (2022). Environmental damages due to war in Ukraine: A perspective. *Science of the Total Environment*, 850. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.157955>

³² Pereira, P., Bašić, F., Bogunovic, I., & Barcelo, D. (2022). Russian-Ukrainian war impacts the total environment. *Science of the Total Environment*, 837. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.155865>

prerequisite for compliance with generally accepted humanitarian norms and propose the integration of a system of serious international liability for crimes leading to environmental disasters during hostilities.

In the publication of Bowden and Metcalfe-Hough,³⁴ the analysis of the effectiveness of humanitarian diplomacy during armed conflicts and wars allows us to focus on existing problems in the legal regulation of humanitarian requirements. The authors' proposal on the need Expanding the scope of responsibility for failure to comply with the guarantees of generally accepted humanitarian principles is seen as particularly relevant. It is obvious that the current sectoral legislation does not meet the needs of responding to challenges of the time, and therefore the objects of regulation of humanitarian law often do not correspond to the legal means and instruments applied to this object.

The scientific research of Dill and Schubiger³⁵ positions the ineffective interdisciplinary potential as the main obstacle to the active interaction of world leaders of international settlement with the parties to the military conflict towards ensuring generally accepted humanitarian norms of the civilian population. The summaries of the scientists presented in the conclusions of the above-mentioned publications are assimilated to the results of this study and actualize the issue of the ineffectiveness of political and technical support for the system of guarantees of humanitarian law.

Al-Gharawi,³⁶ in the process of analytical comparison of systems of guarantees of compliance with generally accepted norms of humanitarian law, argue for the need to establish strict obligations for institutions to comply with international norms and requirements. The scientist draws special attention to the categorical prohibition of the use of torture, coercion, hostage-taking, collective punishment, deportation of civilians during armed conflicts and proposes the introduction of strict sanctions against violators of these requirements. As events in Ukraine show, it is necessary to expand the list of these prohibitions with the risks of a humanitarian catastrophe.

The position of Levy³⁷ is particularly significant, focusing scientific research on aspects of the process of documenting war crimes. The author considers monitoring to be an effective means of preventing the destructive consequences of war for the civilian population and creating certain guarantees of compliance with the generally accepted humanitarian requirements and norms. The opinion of Levy³⁸ is positioned as particularly valuable in regulating the institutional provision of humanitarian law during

³³ Bowden, M., & Metcalfe-Hough, V. (2020). Humanitarian diplomacy and protection advocacy in an age of caution. *HPG Briefing Note*, ODI.

³⁴ Bowden and Metcalfe-Hough, *Humanitarian diplomacy and protection advocacy*, 2020.

³⁵ Dill and Schubiger (2021), "Attitudes toward the use of force," 612–33.

³⁶ Al-Gharawi, F. (2020). Protecting civil and cultural objects under the provisions of the international humanitarian law. *Journal of Misan Comparative Legal Studies*, 1(2).

³⁷ Levy, B. (2023). Documenting and preventing the impacts of war. *Journal of Public Health Policy*, 44, 211–213. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41271-023-00377-0>

³⁸ Levy, "Documenting and preventing the impacts of war," 2023.

the war in Ukraine, where war crimes have become commonplace. An effective system of operational documentation of violations, using modern digital tools, can shape the prerequisites for creating a reliable evidence base of offenses and war crimes during wartime.

Most scholars are unanimous in the direction of prioritizing humanitarian guarantees and positioning them as the highest value, including in conditions of martial law. Without excluding the possibility of certain restrictions established by the international legal field, humanitarian law must provide guarantees of their determination exclusively by legislative norms and prevent unlawful actions of the parties to the conflict, and exclude the possibility of the use of cruel or degrading treatment.

CONCLUSION

5. The current geopolitical situation reflects the inability of established international legal institutions to guarantee the observance of fundamental humanitarian rights during armed conflicts. Both prisoners of war and civilians not taking part in hostilities are subject to numerous violations of generally accepted humanitarian guarantees and do not find adequate protection in the modern legal field. This necessitates the upgrade of international sanctions policy towards the implementation of strict limits on the responsibility of parties to conflicts for violations of universal humanitarian guarantees. The functionality of global institutions in the context of sanctions policy currently requires revision and updating.

Research into major violations of generally accepted norms of humanitarian law during the war in Ukraine indicates the paramount relevance guarantees of humanitarian access and overcoming terrorism. The events in Ukraine should serve as a tragic incentive for improving the system of international humanitarian law. Optimization industry international legislation should be carried out in the direction of guaranteeing the protection of the norms and requirements of humanitarian law, strengthening responsibility for violations, and minimizing all possibilities of using bypass methods.

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